

Can information change preferences for higher education? Evidence from a randomised experiment in Colombia

Gloria L. Bernal¹, Luz K. Abadia¹, Sergio Arango², Kristof De Witte^{3,4}

1. Pontificia Universidad Javeriana. Department of Economics, Bogotá, Colombia.
2. Stanford University, California, USA.
3. Leuven Economics of Education Research, Faculty of Economics and Business, KU Leuven, Belgium.
4. Maastricht University, The Netherlands.

Summary

1. We explore how providing information influences higher education preferences among low-income students in Colombia.
 2. We conducted a randomized controlled trial and discrete choice experiment with 2,652 10th-grade students.
 3. Information on financial aid and tuition costs increased preferences for higher-quality institutions and decreased preferences for public institutions, aligning with real enrollment decisions.
 4. Low-income students showed a willingness to bear about one-third of the tuition costs to attend a high-quality institution instead of a low-quality one.
 5. Recommendations include targeted information campaigns on financial aid, focusing on females and low-SES students, and developing sustainable financial policies with income-contingent repayment plans to support future scholarships.
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1. Introduction

The provision of information can significantly impact students' decision-making processes regarding higher education choices, especially among those from lower-income backgrounds. In developing countries, low-income students often lack critical information about the higher education system (Peter & Zambre, 2017), which affects their preferences, decisions, and aspirations. The research study by Bernal, Abadia, Arango & De Witte (2024) aims to determine whether providing basic information on higher education could alter students' preferences and trade-offs among various higher education attributes, including quality, location, public/private status, scholarships, and subsidies offered.

This policy brief summarizes the findings on how information influences preferences and trade-offs for higher education attributes. Using a randomized controlled trial, the results provide causal evidence rather than mere correlations. Additionally, by following individuals up to their actual higher education choices, the study links hypothetical preference results to real-world decisions, offering robust insights into the impact of information provision.

2. Data and Methodology

Our study involved 2,652 10th-grade low-income Colombian students from 102 schools. The Randomised Controlled Trial methodology that we followed utilizes two treatment groups and one control group. We provided students in the treatment groups with seven statements presenting basic definitions and general facts about higher education. The first treatment group received information emphasizing the returns to attending and the enrollment rates of

accredited higher education institutions (HEIs). In contrast, the second treatment group received information focusing on financial aid and tuition costs at HEIs. Students in the control group received no information.

To measure students' preferences, we conducted a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE). This experiment elicited preferences for five higher education attributes: institution quality, location, type (public or private), scholarship size, and living expense stipend. Students were presented with nine choice sets, each containing two options, to measure their preferences both with and without the provision of information (see Figure 1).

We administered the survey online in the second semester of 2018. Additionally, we collected follow-up data on actual higher education enrollment choices using administrative records.

Our analytical approach consisted of two stages. In the first stage, we evaluated students' preferences using the DCE methodology. The second stage involved assessing the impact of information provision on the importance of each higher education attribute by using interaction terms in the random utility model. Furthermore, we conducted a "Willingness to Give Up" analysis to calculate the percentage of a full scholarship that students were willing to forgo for changes in HEI characteristics. A follow-up was also conducted on the actual choices made by the surveyed individuals, which were documented in administrative records.

3. Results

Providing information on basic information of higher education had a notable effect on students' preferences for higher education institutions. Students who received information about financial aid and tuition costs showed a significant increase in preference for higher-quality institutions compared to the control group. Both treatment groups exhibited a decreased preference for public institutions, suggesting that information about financial aid and costs can shift preferences towards private and higher-quality institutions (see Figure 2). These results align with previous studies showing that information on financial aid can significantly influence enrollment decisions (e.g., Booij et al., 2012; Avitabile & De Hoyos, 2018).

The impact of information was more pronounced among females and students from vulnerable socioeconomic backgrounds. These groups showed a greater shift in their preferences towards higher-quality institutions when provided with financial aid information. This highlights the importance of targeted information campaigns for these demographics, who are often more sensitive to financial constraints and less informed about educational opportunities (Hastings et al., 2016). Students who were initially less informed about higher education showed more significant changes in their preferences when exposed to information. This underscores the potential of reducing informational barriers to effectively alter educational preferences and increase enrollment among less informed students.

Follow-up data on actual enrollment revealed that 29.7% of the surveyed students enrolled in higher education within two years of the intervention. Students who received information about financial aid and tuition

costs were 5.8 percentage points more likely to enroll in higher education compared to the control group. Treated students who enrolled were more likely to choose accredited and private institutions, indicating a lasting impact of information provision on enrollment decisions. These findings are consistent with studies showing that better-informed students are more likely to enroll in higher education (Bettinger et al., 2012; Hastings et al., 2015).

Finally, the "Willingness to Give Up" analysis showed that students were willing to forgo a significant portion of a full scholarship to attend higher-quality institutions. Specifically, they were willing to give up 36% of a full scholarship to switch from a low-quality institution to the highest-quality one, with an even higher willingness observed in Treatment Group 2.

4. Policy recommendations

The results suggest that policymakers can significantly improve outcomes by correcting informational asymmetries. Some specific measures include:

First, enhance and target information campaigns on higher education. Implement comprehensive information campaigns that focus on financial aid availability, education costs, and clarifications on educational tracks and accredited institutions. Use clear, accessible language and interactive formats, like the 'Myth or Reality' activity, to reduce misconceptions and help students make informed decisions. Additionally, design targeted campaigns for females and students from vulnerable socioeconomic backgrounds. Tailored messages should address their specific concerns and barriers, helping them make informed decisions about their educational futures. Conduct regular information sessions in low-income schools to

significantly increase knowledge and influence higher education decisions. Embedding these sessions into the school curriculum ensures all students have access to essential information.

Second, promote sustainable financial policies. Assuming students have clear financial information and financial aid is widely promoted, develop new sustainable policies that allocate part of loan repayments to a fund for future students. For instance, the Ser Pilo Paga program in Colombia provided full tuition coverage for top-performing, low-income students. Despite its success, it ended due to budget constraints. A sustainable alternative would be income-contingent repayment plans, where graduates pay a percentage of their future income to settle their debt. This model ensures a continuous flow of funds to support new students.

Third, monitor and evaluate students' trajectories. Establish systems to monitor low-income students' preferences, provide them clear information on the entire higher education system, and track the effectiveness of successfully navigating the system. Regularly evaluate enrollment rates and the types of institutions chosen. Use this data to refine and improve campaigns and policies, ensuring they effectively address students' needs and promote higher education access.

What is EFFEct ?

EFFEct is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

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Figures

Figure 1. Activity instructions to the students before starting the DCE and an example of a DCE choice set.

ACTIVITY		
<p>In the next activity you have to choose the higher education bundle that, you would prefer (Bundle 1 or Bundle 2). The scenarios are imaginary, and refer to institutions of higher education (for example, universities or university of applied sciences). Each option has 5 attributes:</p>		
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Quality of the Higher Education Institution: Where 5 stars is the highest quality and 2 stars is the minimum quality. The accredited higher education institutions have 4 or 5 stars and those not accredited have 2 or 3 stars. Location of the higher education institution: This represents the number of hours by bus that you would have to take from your city of origin to the city where the higher education institution is located. Type of higher education institution: public or private. Scholarship for tuition payment: This represents the percentage that is given to subsidize your enrollment. If the scholarship is NOT 100%, you are supposed to pay the rest of the tuition when you graduate and receive a salary. Support Subsidy: "YES" means that you are provided by a subsidy of \$ 312,000 per month for transport, food and housing expenses. "NO" means that you do not receive extra money. 		
<p>1/9. Assuming you're accepted in the program you like the most (in 2 different institutions), which one of the following bundles would you prefer?</p>		
Attribute	Bundle 1	Bundle 2
Quality of HEIs		
Location of HEIs	The city where you live	2 hours in bus from where you live. Move or not.
Type of HEIs	Private	Public
Scholarship (%)	Scholarship: 50% 50% - The remaining 50%, you will be able to pay back by giving up 20% of your salary received for 5 years after graduation.	Scholarship: 0% 0% - The 100%, you will be able to pay back by giving up 20% of your salary received for 9 years after graduation.
Subsidy	NO	yes = \$312.000 monthly (108USD)
<p>Which one do you prefer? <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/></p>		

Note: original text in Spanish. After instructions, and according to their preferences, students must choose between the two possible bundles of higher education displayed in each of the nine choicest.

Figure 2. Effect of information on preferences for higher education attributes

Note: Treatment 1 offers general information of higher education with emphasis on returns and access. Treatment 2 offers general information of higher education with emphasis credits and costs. Dots with horizontal lines indicate point estimates with choice-set fixed effect, cluster standard error at school level and 90% confidence intervals from least squares regression. The references categories for each attribute-level is: 2 stars, private HEI, no stipend, 0 hours away from home, and the interaction of those reference categories times each treatment. Attributes*Treatment1 refers to the interaction between each attribute-level and treatment 1 dummy. Attributes*Treatment2 refers to the interaction between each attribute-level and treatment 2 dummy. Appendix Table B displays the underlying regression results.

Further Information:

Bernal, G. L., Abadia, L. K., Arango, S., & De Witte, K. (2024). Can information change preferences for higher education? Evidence from a randomised experiment in Colombia. *International Journal of Educational Development*. In Press.

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